

IPv4/IPv6 dual stack

Checking service consistency

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ABSTRACT

Multiple CERN's servers are configured with both IPv4 and IPv6. Consistency of the configuration for both needs to be ensured in order to provide stability and security.

All the servers with IPv4 and IPv6 configurations should run the same set of services in both protocols and have the same firewall configuration.

To achieve the above, I have developed an application which checks for inconsistencies and differences between the IPv4 and IPv6 configurations and generates reports. Those reports will help configuring and securing the servers correctly.

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1. INTRODUCTION

CERN has multiple servers, which are configured with both IPv4 and IPv6. A correctly configured server with IPv6 enabled should have the same set of network services listening on IPv4 and on IPv6. Also, it should have the same or similar local firewall configurations.

Configuration inconsistencies -- like different services, ports, websites or contents -- introduce possible security vulnerabilities and make the protection of the servers even harder.

The objective of my project is to write a script that automatically reviews the security footprint of such servers by comparing IPv4 and IPv6 firewall rules and report discrepancies.

2. IMPLEMENTATION

a. Overview

The project is implemented in Python 2.7 and no additional libraries were used. The script parses two files that contain the IPv4 and IPv6 firewall filters and rules. The filters and rules for both IPv4 and IPv6 are stored in dictionaries.

After parsing the files, the following checks are executed:

- **Inconsistency check in Filters and Rules definitions**
- **Level 1 filters comparison**
- **Level 2 filters comparison**
- **Rules comparison**

After all the checks are executed two HTML reports are generated (one which contains all the filters and rules and one which contains only inconsistencies).

b. Classes

i. Filter

The “Filter” class represents a firewall filter and it contains the following attributes:

- **name**: name of the filter
- **level**: level of the filter (1 or 2)
- **type**: type of the filter
- **default**: default policy of the filter
- **status**: status of the filter
- **number_of_filters**: number of sub- filters the filter contains
- **number_of_rules**: number of rules the filter contains

ii. Rule

The “Rule” class represents a firewall rules and it contains the following attributes:

- **policy**: policy of the rule (permit or deny)
- **protocol**: protocol of the rule
- **source**: source IP or name
- **destination**: destination IP or name
- **status**: status of the rule
- **number_of_rules**: number of rules the rule contains
- **bidirectional**: Boolean attribute, true if the rule is bidirectional

c. Functions

i. fw-rules-cmp.py

- **main**

ii. parser.py

- **is_rule**: returns true if a line is a rule, false otherwise
- **is_bidirectional**: returns true if a line is a bidirectional rule, false otherwise
- **is_set_of_rules**: returns true if a line is a set of rule, false otherwise
- **l_level**: returns the hierarchical position of a line
- **parse_fw_file**: parses a file that contain firewall rules and returns two dictionaries that contain level 1 filters, level 2 filters and rules

iii. report.py

- **consistency_check**: checks if filters/rules contain the declared number of filters /rules and returns a string that contains the report in HTML
- **compare_level_1_filters**: compares level 1 filters and returns a string that contains the report in HTML
- **compare_level_2_filters**: compares level 2 filters and returns a string that contains the report in HTML
- **rule_contains_ip_only**: returns true if a rule's source or destination contain only an IP address and not a name
- **compare_rules**: compares rules and returns a string that contains the report in HTML
- **generate_report**: generates the HTML report

3. RESULTS AND FUTURE WORK

After completing the application and running it on the IPv4 and IPv6 firewall rules, several inconsistencies and differences were reported.

The consistency check on each file reported that the number of declared rules and the actual number of rules that several filters contained was different. That behavior was mostly observed in filters that exist in both the IPv4 and IPv6 rules. There are two different causes for the problem stated above:

- If there is the same filter in the IPv4 and IPv6 rules then the same number of rules is declared in both but each contain only the rules for the IPv4 or IPv6 respectively;
- Some filters contain duplicates of the same filter or rule.

Also, there were discrepancies found between the IPv4 and IPv6 sets of rules.

The problems stated above were reported to CERN's network group in order to get fixed.

4. REFERENCES

- <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/ComputerSecurity/ProceduresFirewall>
- <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/ComputerSecurity/DocumentsFirewall>
- **git repository:** <https://gitlab.cern.ch/ComputerSecurity/fw-rules-cmp>

